

Transforming Healthcare in Sri Lanka: *Achieving Sustainable Development and Global Health Equity Through User-Centric Technology Integration*

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Sri Lanka

Population¹: 22.1 M
Literacy rate²: 92.64%
Computer literacy: 39%
Digital Literacy: 63.5%
Mobile penetration³: 131.5%
Smartphone penetration³: 65.7% (out of all phones)
Desktop/laptop ownership: 20.2% of households
Internet Penetration⁴: ~ 56%
Fixed operator ARPU⁵: < 7.5 USD
Mobile operator ARPU⁵: < 1.5 USD

Sources:

1. Department of Census and Statistics (DCS),

2.

[https://countrymeters.info/en/Sri_Lanka#:~:text=Literacy%20of%20population,93.63%25%20\(7%2C397%2C885%20persons\).](https://countrymeters.info/en/Sri_Lanka#:~:text=Literacy%20of%20population,93.63%25%20(7%2C397%2C885%20persons).)

3. <https://www.trc.gov.lk/content/files/statistics/Telecom%20Statistics%20of%20Sri%20Lanka.Q1.pdf>

4. <https://datareportal.com/reports/digital-2024-sri-lanka>

5. https://www.trc.gov.lk/content/files/reports/AR_2021_E.pdf

Source: <https://www.health.gov.lk/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/Digital-Health-Blue-Print-Full-Book-01.11.2023-Final.pdf> (Ruins of a 2,000-year-old hospital in the historical city of Anuradhapura)

Source: <https://www.sundaytimes.lk/230205/sunday-times-2/evolution-of-the-healthcare-system-510704.html>

Sri Lanka Digital Health Blueprint

- *“Enabling a Healthier Nation through Digital Transformation of Healthcare”*

Achievements

- Revolutionized Health Information System (**HIS**)
- Addressed challenges of paper-based systems
- Initiated **healthcare digitalization** in the early 2010s
- Adopted **Health Informatics specialty**
- Implemented HIS in 85+ state hospitals¹
- Registered 12+ million patients

Proposed Initiatives

- Develop a comprehensive Digital Health Blueprint (**DHB**)
- Establish National Electronic Health Record (**NeHR**)
- Create a comprehensive **Digital Health Platform**
- Implement a phased approach to sustainability
- Align future investments with DHB

Source: Health Information Unit Ministry of Health (Publication date: November 2023) =

<https://www.health.gov.lk/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/Digital-Health-Blue-Print-Full-Book-01.11.2023-Final.pdf>

Notes: Out of 555 Government Hospitals (<https://www.health.gov.lk/health-institutions-in-sri-lanka/>)

Source: <https://www.health.gov.lk/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/Digital-Health-Blue-Print-Full-Book-01.11.2023-Final.pdf>

Drugs availability

i For accurate information on stock availability please use the Correct generic name of the item with the correct dosage form /size/type or the SR (Stock Reference) no.

Actions	Item Code	Name	MSD Stock	Other Institution Stock	National Stock
	00700401	Metformin Tablet 500mg	12,417,000.00	126,446,232.00	138,863,232.00
	00700402	Metformin sustain release tablet 850mg	0.00	0	0
	00700403	Metformin Modified release Tablet 500mg	2,000.00	3,275,467.00	3,277,467.00
	05007001	Sitagliptin 100mg and Metformin Hydrochloride 1000mg Extended Release Tablet	0.00	0	0
		Metformin SR (Glycomet SR)	0.00	0	0

Source: https://swastha.health.gov.lk/drugs_availability/

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Sri Lanka Telecom

- National ICT solutions provider and the leading broadband and backbone infrastructure services provider of Sri Lanka

Source: Sri Lanka Telecom PLC – Annual Report 2023

ESG strategy closely aligned with UN SDGs

Nature		Education	Health	Sponsorships
SLT Green Initiatives		Empowering Smart Education	Health and Wealth for Society	Community Engagement
Tree planting		Hackathon	Equipment donations	Entertainment
Online awareness		Book donations	Digital inclusion	Cultural and religious events
Emissions assessment		Smart classrooms		Exhibitions and other social gatherings
Waste management		Infrastructure investment		
		Skill development programmes		

Source: Sri Lanka Telecom PLC – Annual Report 2023

- Since 2001
- 1st software development and ICT service provider to enter the digital healthcare industry in Sri Lanka
- Providing digital lifestyle solutions for healthcare and other industries

Source: <https://www.echannelling.com/>

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Source: <https://www.echannelling.com/>

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Source: <https://www.echannelling.com/>

Summary

- Sri Lanka has a long and rich history of healthcare
- Sri Lanka healthcare digitalization - started in 2010, has a long way to go
- A DHB is in place and the citizens are well equipped
- A User-Centric Technology Integration is needed to deliver cost-effective healthcare services
- SLT-MOBITEL provides Digital Healthcare services through E-Channeling while providing the necessary Digital Infrastructure for National Health

Towards a healthier nation.

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Lotus tower - Photo by Christoph Theisinger on Unsplash